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D1.1 – Updated specification of development process

WP1: Code Optimization & Scaling

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Executive Summary

This document describes the current state and planning of the software engineering tasks within BioExcel2 WP1¹. The quality assurance (QA) and testing practices for the application software GROMACS, HADDOCK and CP2K, as well as the GROMACS linked input preparation tool PMX are described. The plans on how to continue the implementation of software engineering best practices are outlined for the projects, to ensure that the planned improvements for usability, scalability and performance do not negatively affect the correctness of the software codes and their associated web portals.

In addition, this document reports on initial benchmarking and profiling of QM/MM biomolecular simulations in CP2K, which is critically important for BioExcel to understand how to produce high impact in this area. While such simulations have tremendous potential for impact at the exascale, biomolecular QM/MM is not as mature as e.g. classical MD or docking; all work in this area carries both high risk and reward. Very limited experience exists among biomolecular simulation users and developers, including within the BioExcel consortium.

The report includes details of the work undertaken, presented to illustrate the approaches used, including development of appropriate test cases, and the approaches used to ensure that the results obtained from (short) test cases are meaningful for production simulation runs. In the short period of time available, scaling graphs and profiles have been obtained. Scaling results have demonstrated limited scaling, consistent with several existing CP2K benchmarks which are based on similar system sizes. For these kinds of problems, CP2K does not appear to currently scale well beyond about 16 nodes, notably worse than the headline scalability figures often quoted for CP2K on other problem types. Several relevant routines have been identified for further investigation, but initial results indicate that improving scaling on these problems could be challenging. To mitigate the risk associated with investing time on the code with limited return, the consortium has agreed a future checkpoint at PM8 for a final decision on whether further effort should be invested in optimization of CP2K for biomolecular QM/MM.

¹ The current version is a revision based on the reviewers' comments.

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Introduction

The core applications in BioExcel (GROMACS, QM/MM CP2K, and HADDOCK) are committed to delivering high quality life-science software that meets its users' needs by following accepted best practice in software engineering, to the extent that available resources permit.

Much scientific software is written to serve the needs of a single researcher or a single short-term research project, and it can be appropriate to write such code without considering whether it will be re-used. [1-3] However, some of the core codes for BioExcel have matured to the point where they serve the needs of thousands of life scientists, and the success of the consortium depends on expanding the user base and range of quality software that serves it. Each code may be exposed to hardware and software changes during the transition from peta- to exascale era. These concerns strongly suggest a more professional approach to justify the investment of further development resources, and to reduce the risk associated with widespread use. The software development within BioExcel will incorporate existing recommendations for best practice for scientific computing.[4]

Among the challenges, the diverse applications within BioExcel are:

- written in different programming languages
- matured independently and to different extents
- addressing different kinds of biomolecular simulation problem
- delivered to end users differently
- implemented by small numbers of software developers located at different institutions

Therefore, no software-engineering process can be applied uniformly across BioExcel. This document will describe the processes that we have determined to be beneficial to unified across the consortium. It will also record the details of the state and plans for the sub-teams within the consortium. This record will serve as a model for future improvements within the teams, for expansion to include new teams, and future unification of elements that become common to sub-teams. In our judgement, the needs of BioExcel users are best served by each sub-team evolving its process independently; we do not intend to evolve a single common process.

Much has been written about how to implement best practice in software engineering. Best practice in this field is also evolving rapidly as the hardware, languages and tools evolve. One important work identified seven basic principles for successful large-scale commercial software delivery [5]. The first four of these are applicable to the software engineering effort in BioExcel, and are consistent with published best practice for scientific software development [4].

The following provides a description of each principle, and the way in which the BioExcel software development will address them is described in *italics*. These approaches will be expanded upon in the following sections for the core codes.

1. Manage using a **phased life-cycle plan**, to specify what will be done, recognizing that effort in design phases leads to shorter coding, debugging and validation times.

The Description of Action and Deliverable 1.1 forms part of that plan for the overall consortium. For each new feature, individual sub-teams within BioExcel will produce written plans on ClickUp and consult with other teams on the kinds of high-level aspects where independent perspective can lead to better development results.

2. Perform **continuous validation** after having agreed on expectations for the software, to review progress, and automatically test results.

Each BioExcel software sub-team will develop or expand automated techniques for testing their software for desirable properties such as correctness or performance. This is a key requirement for all kinds of software, but scientific user communities make particular demands for it, and our development processes will specifically address it.

3. Maintain disciplined **product control**, in particular to avoid opportunistic changes to the plan, or promising more than the available developer effort will permit.

Resources are limited and the scope of the work within the Description of Action is large, so the BioExcel software development efforts will need to choose manageable sub-projects with a view to being able to deliver quality software in suitable graduations over the lifetime of the project. This will permit the consortium to show value in the hands of users by the time of the final review, and ensures that some software will be delivered even if progress in some aspects is slower than anticipated.

4. Use **modern programming practices**, in particular to use development techniques such as encapsulation, modularity, version control, issue tracking, code review, automated code analysis, and unit testing to make most efficient use of time in the long term.

These are well established and standardized techniques that BioExcel developers will follow because they provide demonstrated value in producing software that is correct, can be maintained and extended, and which provide resilience in the face of anticipated changes to hardware and libraries as we approach the exascale era. Different approaches will be employed by each sub-team to suit the needs of software delivered in different ways and written in different languages.

In BioExcel-1, we consulted with the UK-based *Software Sustainability Institute* (<https://www.software.ac.uk/>) to get valuable input from them into our software-engineering process. Representatives of BioExcel have attended SSI events, and our teams follow the excellent advice from many of their guides (<https://www.software.ac.uk/resources/guides>). We will continue to collaborate with SSI to ensure our knowledge stays current.

New software functionality will be made available in their respective repositories, as well as in project deliverables after 18 and 36 months, and will be reported in scientific publications authored by BioExcel participants. It is however recognized that the true utility of scientific software is that it permits its users to innovate effectively [2]. Demonstrating the quality of the output of the software can be more important than new functionality, particularly if it permits users to adopt more recent versions of the software with confidence that old results are reproducible, or clearly corrected. In BioExcel, the quality of the software output will be assured through extensive testing, monitored via feedback from the BioExcel user communities, and feedback used to

guide future development efforts. New software and modules developed within BioExcel will be released under OSI-approved open source licenses such as Lesser GNU Public License (LGPL) or Apache License.

1. Status at the beginning of BioExcel-2

Overview

Three of the four core applications in BioExcel-2 have been part of the first phase of the project, BioExcel-1. Although the applications are at different levels of maturity concerning software development standards, and also of different size in terms of code and user base, we have all gained valuable insights and improved processes during the first phase.

Software developed by scientists using public, including EU, funding should be open source. Thus, we have adopted open source licensing for the whole code bases, or at a minimum for parts developed within BioExcel where the original code used a more restrictive license. Periodic releases of the codes are made available through bioexcel.eu and hosted on [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/).

Highlights from BioExcel-1 phase

Both scaling, high-end performance and throughput of the pilot codes (GROMACS, HADDOCK, and CPMD) were improved significantly - in some cases more than doubled – which has had large impact on usage ranging from high-end PRACE systems to research labs and industry. The codes were prepared for exascale-era biomolecular simulations by establishing documented software development processes and QA, which is now being shared with other scientific codes (as an example, the BioExcel-initiated collaboration on GPU-acceleration of the cryo-EM code RELION has had very large impact on the cryo-EM community). Key kernels were ported to run on hardware expected to feature in the European pre-exascale and exascale landscape, targeting all current accelerator and CPU platforms, including close co-design collaborations with multiple hardware vendors. Web-based portals were updated to provide an excellent user experience. All core applications started identifying new user-requested features through interactions with the communities and implemented them to serve the scientific needs of users, particularly to support efficient and usable ensemble and free-energy calculations. A pre-exascale benchmark of an example use case was performed and reported. All applications now have development road maps targeting both exascale and industry usage.

Gathering requirements and support

We learned that we needed to develop systematic processes to collect feature requests and follow up on those. Most scientific codes start out small, often initially only being used in a single group, and then the needs are clear. But as the number of users grows, it quickly becomes difficult to manage the needs of the users. In BioExcel we have developed and described the processes to collect user requirements and follow up on those, either implementing or rejecting them. This process is further described section 2 below.

For user support we set up in BioExcel-1 Discourse forums at ask.bioexcel.eu. All pilot applications, except for GROMACS, use this unified support forum for their user support. GROMACS already had an extensively used mailing lists which we did not want to abandon without careful discussions with the users and the many people who answer questions. The GROMACS forums are linked on ask.bioexcel.eu. The decision was made to replace the GROMACS user mailing list by a discourse forum on bioexcel.eu, which has now been implemented under BioExcel-2.

Development planning

Although gathering needs of users is very important, as stated before, these cannot be the only drivers of development of scientific software. Users usually request (more of) what they know about, whereas science progresses by developing new methods. Also support for future hardware, e.g. exascale machines, requires a lot of development resources. Developers should weigh these three different needs against each other and make well balanced decisions on how to best allocate their, often scarce, resources. As software needs to run well on upcoming (pre-)exascale machines, this has particular high priority in BioExcel-2.

In order to make clear what was the status of the code at the end of the first BioExcel project and at the current stage in BioExcel-2 (i.e. to highlight the new developments), annexes for each code are provided in this document. For HADDOCK, both the further development of the 2.4 code and web portal, the official production version, and the new, complete modular rewrite under BioExcel-2 (haddock3), the status at the start and the planning for month 18 of the project are described in Annexes 1-3. For GROMACS, the code and modular code development status are reported in Annexes 4-5. Annexes 6 and 7 report on the status and planning for PMX and CP2K, respectively.

Recommendations and future work

BioExcel is an advocate and promoter of best practices for software development. During BioExcel-1 we wrote and published a whitepaper on scientific software development (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1194634>). The whitepaper covers all aspects of software development and maintenance, many of which are applicable to software development in general and some which are more specific to scientific software. We are following the recommendations from the whitepaper and have improved the development processes of all core codes. There are plans to release an update of the white paper in the second half of the current BioExcel-2 phase, as well as to produce an educational webinar on the topic.

Based on our experience, we have outlined in the introductory section (page 8) several core principles which encompass the main aspects of code development. We recommend that every development group applies those in their practice. It will be needed to select a suitable development model (see e.g. <http://oro.open.ac.uk/17673/>) which reflects the size, structure and routines of the group.

2. Gathering user requirements to aid planning

The major unifying thread across the BioExcel software development teams is that they include practicing scientists with experience of using a range of scientific software to

solve biomolecular problems, and developers of such software. It is widely agreed that effort spent in planning phases of software development projects delivers tangible benefits in the form of faster progression through coding, testing and acceptance phases [6]. The BioExcel development sub-teams will conduct feature development after a planning phase that includes:

- consulting with prospective users about functionality changes,
- assessing that the available coding resources are adequate,
- deciding that potential risks to the usefulness of the software once complete are acceptable,
- drafting a user interface, and
- producing a written plan on the BioExcel task-management system *ClickUp*.

In particular, the draft user interfaces and development plans will be shared across the software-development teams for feedback on the proposed user interface, and development plan. This leverages the different experience and perspective of developers from other sub-teams to add useful value via this form of peer review. Prospective users will also be consulted to improve the chances that the implementation is fit for its purpose. It is expected that success of this model within BioExcel will motivate other developers within the broader application development teams to participate and perhaps provide a consultative service to the broader biomolecular simulation software development community. We will monitor and report on this process internally and at formal project reviews.

3. GROMACS development process

GROMACS [7] is a molecular dynamics simulation engine that can simulate the Newtonian equations of motion for systems with hundreds to millions of particles. It is primarily designed for simulations of biochemical molecules like proteins, lipids and nucleic acids, which have a lot of complicated bonded interactions. Its chief virtue is that it is extremely fast at calculating the non-bonded interactions necessary for such systems. It is a state-of-the-art best-in-class implementation of molecular dynamics, with high-performance implementations for a wide range of commodity CPUs and GPUs, including all current and several anticipated future HPC platforms. It is in use by thousands of scientists, leading to more than 11 citations per day of associated scientific articles.

Figure 1 depicts the current state of GROMACS code development process. Having made appropriate plans before writing code, developers upload proposed changes for review on our Gerrit code-review server, triggering automated continuous-integration testing via Jenkins, and awaiting review from other developers. Automatic cross-references to the Redmine bug reports and feature requests are made. Once code is accepted into the master branch of the repository, it is automatically pushed to our GitHub backup repository.

Figure 1 Current GROMACS development workflow description.

3.1 Copyright and License under GPL2.1

GROMACS is released under the Lesser GNU General Public License (LGPL) v2.1 (or later). Each source code file has a copyright statement, which is automatically updated for each applicable year that it changes, which is necessary for the license to be effective. Source tarballs contain the appropriate COPYING file, that additionally notes the origin of code bundled along with GROMACS, and the license under which it is redistributed.

It is our understanding that this open source license permits unrestricted (including commercial) linking to the library as well as free or commercial modification or redistribution.

3.2 Software Architecture

GROMACS includes a high-performance simulation engine *mdrun*, several independent tools for preparing simulations, and a suite of around 50 post-simulation analysis packages. Currently all are run on a command-line terminal from a common *gmx* wrapper binary by naming the required sub-tool. This provides a small surface area for potential conflicts with other software on a user's system, and many convenient features including the ability to deprecate or rename tools while still retaining a way for users to learn whether and where the old functionality is still available. Much of the approximately 2 million lines of code is specific to *mdrun*, and much is shared across all the tools, and the long-term future of the package will require extensive reorganization to reflect which components support which functionality and thus

require particular focus when developing and maintaining the software. The *mdrun* tool will be decomposed into several disjoint tools to improve usability and make it easier to learn. As the underlying library matures, it may be feasible to expand the existing auto-tuning framework to make it easier for users to get the maximum performance available.

The current development plans are to separate parts of the functionality currently bundled in *gmx mdrun* to individual tools. This aims to reduce the possibility of using functionality in unintended ways by providing clear tool names that precisely match the functionality provided. Those plans have been announced in the deprecation notes of the recent GROMACS 2019 release.

3.3 Handling of new user feature requests

Current: Anyone, including regular developers, may search and open issues at <https://redmine.gromacs.org> to seek interest, find common ground and identify strategies. Usually proceeding to actual development will require someone actively finding a source of funding and a suitably experienced developer, and enough time and enthusiasm in the rest of the developer community for testing and code review.

Future: In future phases of BioExcel, provide opportunity for clients to discuss e.g. development of new features on a contract basis.

3.4 Handling of Bug tracking

The Redmine server <https://redmine.gromacs.org> also allows any user to register an account and file a bug report, along with uploaded input files. Developers regularly browse for relevant issues and engage in productive discussions with the reporter(s) and each other. When fixes are uploaded for code review, they can cross-reference the bug report, and automatic HTML cross links are created. Release notes can then note that the bug was fixed and provide links to more detail as required.

3.5 Versioning policy

Current: GROMACS numbers each release as *year.patch* (e.g. 2019.1) so that it is clear to users how old their baseline version is, and that the release was made because it was time to do the annual release. It is generally recognized that software development can produce only two out of three of *high quality*, *on time*, or specified *functionality*; therefore we focus on the former two so that users can regularly benefit from new functionality that has been completed, without risk of open-ended waiting for other functionality. This provides the wider development team with confidence that an accepted feature will get into the hands of users early without having to wait for completion of other planned features.

Future: No changes are planned. Current resources do not permit more than one annual major release. Patch releases will continue to happen for the currently supported version in 2 – 3 months intervals.

3.5.1 Handling of Version Control

Git is used for version control. All code development should start from the official git repository (git.gromacs.org) or one of its mirrors (including <https://github.com/gromacs/>). Developers modifying GROMACS will benefit from being able to use git tools such as *grep* and *rebase* to work with the code. Code development should not start from a release tarball, but if this has happened then it can be copied onto a git repository.

3.5.2 Handling of Released version storage

Formerly: Released versions are stored on ftp.gromacs.org.

Currently: Versions are stored on FTP server and as items on Zenodo, with a citable DOI associated to each version of the source code (e.g. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2564764>) as well as the corresponding manual (e.g. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2564761>).

Future: The project will explore if it is feasible to only store released version on Zenodo or similar hosting services that allow associating the version of the source code/manual with a unique DOI.

3.5.3 Handling of development branches

Formerly: A development-oriented *master* branch as well as stable release-oriented branches exist. The *master* branch is open for both refactoring and functionality changes, including addition and removal of features. Release branches are generated annually and only accept bug fixing, with no other changes to functionality. Bug fixes are generally performed in release branches and merged back into *master*.

Currently: The branch setup is kept, with the addition of *feature development branches* to showcase new functionality. Those branches are not expected to be merged directly into the master branch, rather code present in feature branches can be used to generate and propose smaller changes that can be individually reviewed, tested, and merged into *master*.

Bug fixes are done on the latest supported release branch or in the master branch. If fixes are needed in several separate branches, they will be performed as individual changes to avoid issues during merging of branches.

3.6 Modularization

Current: GROMACS is finalizing the transition from C89 to a modular, unit-tested modern C++14 library. This transition has been slow and costly but has been shown to deliver long-term benefits from lower maintenance, better extensibility and higher portability. The classes within these modules encapsulate behavior alongside the data necessary to implement it, and enable full [Doxygen](#) documentation of files, classes, members and methods. The modules follow a layered design that is enforced by checking scripts.

Future: Draft a target module hierarchy for the wider development community to use as a mental model during the refactoring process.

3.7 Development process details

Current: Developers are generally autonomous academics who propose ideas on the *gmx-developers* mailing list, or on the Redmine server, and other interested developers contribute ideas. Outside BioExcel, these evolve on an ad hoc basis. Developers progress to develop working code which is then uploaded for peer review. Developers can propose code changes that are tagged “*request for comment*” or “*work in progress*” so that reviewers know that high-level feedback is needed. An ongoing challenge is to motivate volunteers in the developer community to contribute to design and review stages in a timely fashion, because most developers are academics with multiple responsibilities and GROMACS development is only a small fraction of their output (and not always clearly recognized for career progression). However, since all developers are subject to the same review and testing process, all do already recognize that nobody can progress in isolation.

Developers require active encouragement to remember to separate changes that refactor the code from those that change the functionality, because the time of code reviewers is a particularly scarce resource, and such separation maximizes the value delivered by reviewer time.

Future: BioExcel developers will lead the way in producing a written plan, in particular for how the user interface will evolve alongside features. Development targets and plans will be announced as tasks on the task management system *ClickUp*, allowing easy assignment of work to individual developers while adding additional ability to provide planning and execution feedback at the level of BioExcel or its external collaborators. The tasks will be linked to the Redmine issues and thus changes on Gerrit to allow tracking of progress during development.

3.7.1 Review Process

Current: All code changes go through two-person review, one core developer, and one other developer. Preferably at least one of those has previously contributed to code in this area, so they are able to make an informed review reasonably efficiently. Review is difficult for both parties, so feedback and responses need to be considered carefully and should be technical and impersonal. Proposed changes do not have to be perfect to pass review, but they should represent a clear improvement in at least some aspect without undue compromise on other aspects. Authors may declare a reviewer suggestion out of their intended scope, in which case the discussion should move to a Redmine issue for future consideration. Authors may negotiate that someone else takes over responsibility for the patch.

Future: The most important quality of scientific code is its correctness at implementing the method claimed. Only a subset of kinds of proposed changes have the ability to compromise this with GROMACS. It is inefficient to require the same level of

developer scrutiny on all changes, particularly when the number of developer hours available to the project is strictly limited. In concert with improved testing, we will identify areas of the code for which greater risk is acceptable, e.g. refactoring of modules already under high quality unit tests or improvements to user or developer documentation.

3.7.2 Approach to integrate new external code

Current: No long-term development branches exist, so proposed code changes are normally based off a recent master-branch commit, and thus can be readily rebased for integration with the current HEAD commit of the master branch.

Future: Some larger development efforts will benefit from the proposed long-running feature branches. While those will not necessarily be integrated directly back into the master branch, they will act as showcase for the new functionality and will allow the generation of smaller changes that can easily be integrated back.

Given the limited developer effort available for code review, the code in feature branches still needs to be presented for review in small pieces that each passes its own unit tests, and any available integration or end-to-end test.

3.7.3 Requirements for software testing

Current: All proposed code changes are tested automatically by our Jenkins continuous-integration server. It builds the code and runs the tests on multiple compilers, operating systems, standard libraries, accelerators and CPU types. This caters directly to ensuring long-term portability of the code base to the anticipated features of the exascale landscape. Several static analysis tools are also run. All tests must pass before a change can be acceptable. The range of tests and tools are reviewed and updated continuously. Fast-running tests run for each proposed code change on important platforms, and slower-running tests also run on a wider range of platforms once the proposed code has been accepted.

See http://jenkins.gromacs.org/job/Documentation_Nightly_master/javadoc/dev-manual/jenkins.html for more details. Released versions, e.g. source tarballs are tested on a range of configurations before release.

Future: Specific activities to be achieved over the course of BioExcel are:

- expanding test coverage,
- replacing old testing Perl driver script with GoogleTest C++ driver,
- deploying automated performance regression testing,
- deploying Docker-based multi-tier CI builds (e.g. with Kubernetes) to streamline the implementation, giving developers faster feedback,
- continuing to add support for warning-free builds for up-to-date compilers, code analyzers, and libraries,
- deploying pre-release testing suite that verifies correctness of ensembles produced, and

- adding support for the Memory, Leak and UndefinedBehaviour Sanitizer code-analysis tools to the CI configuration,
- reporting annual increases in test coverage,
- monitor whether it becomes feasible to make use of freely available CI tools, given that GROMACS has specific testing needs e.g .for GPUs and HPC compilers that are not commonly available.

3.7.4 Code documentation and commenting

Code is commented with a view to explaining what the code is doing, rather than how. If it is not obvious how the code is working, then prefer to improve the naming of variables and methods, use better control flow, or show examples with working tests. New and newly refactored methods and source files must have Doxygen-style comments that are automatically built into the developer guide available at http://jenkins.gromacs.org/job/Documentation_Nightly_master/javadoc/#documentation-for-developers

3.7.5 Coding standards and coding style

Current: The GROMACS style guidelines at http://jenkins.gromacs.org/job/Documentation_Nightly_master/javadoc/dev-manual/style.html show our adherence to the general C++ best practice *CppCoreGuidelines* (<https://github.com/isocpp/CppCoreGuidelines>).

Future: No changes to the general style guide are planned. The project aims to keep in step with the general core guidelines.

3.8 Release process

Current: Formal releases will only be made from release branches and will follow the versioning scheme in use at the time that branch forked from the master branch. Generally, at least one release candidate is made available for the community for around a month of informal testing before the final release. During this time users and developers are encouraged to attempt to validate that their simulations of interest work at least as well (or better) than previously. Debian and Fedora projects already test GROMACS on a wide range of platforms, and they will be invited to help with this effort. The eventual source and tests tarballs for the release are built by Jenkins from a commit in the repository that will later be tagged with the release number. That tarball is automatically tested by the Jenkins continuous-integration server on a range of installation configurations, to verify that the build works and the tests pass. The documentation that matches the release is automatically generated from the tarball and prepared for easy deployment to web servers. The stages of the release process are shared with the wider community through emails to the users, developers and announcement mailing lists, posts on social media outlets (Facebook, Twitter), and both the GROMACS and BioExcel websites.

Future: Finalize automation of final details of an automatic release build, including construction and deployment of the release notes, and embedding tarball checksums in the appropriate locations. The project plans to release newer versions of GROMACS as Docker containers to make it easier for users to use newer versions for testing in a ready-made state.

3.8.1 Deprecation

When a feature is identified as superseded, is no longer functioning, or is lacking developer support for maintenance then it will be deprecated, after due consultation with the user and developer community. Generally, such a feature will be deprecated from the next annual release, so that users who run the code receive advance warning that they are at risk of depending on code that will not be maintained in future major releases. In following annual major releases, the feature may be removed at the discretion of the developer community. When code is found to have been broken for multiple years already, and thus cannot be in active use in a maintained branch, it might be removed without a preceding deprecation notice in the software, but this will be acknowledged in the release notes of the next release. Support for older hardware platforms is also removed gradually in major releases, to make effective use of developer time porting to new hardware; older versions based on previous major releases of the code still run on the older hardware for those who cannot upgrade usefully.

3.8.2 Retirement of old versions

Current: Led by the professional BioExcel support and maintenance team, each (annual) major release is followed by one year of best effort support by developers, to fix any shortcoming in the implementation of functionality intended to be supported in that release. That includes code correctness, accuracy and presence of documentation, functioning of build system, and simulation performance, whether reported by users or developers. The stability of related code paths will form part of the decision about whether, where and how to fix a bug. If a bug fix is not feasible, then the code will be altered to prevent future releases from running any scientifically wrong code, and report this to the user in subsequent bug-fix releases at run time, and document it in release notes. After one year, there will be a further year of best effort to fix any issue that affects scientific correctness (whether in mdrun or tools).

The developers reserve the option to fix a bug only in the master branch if that seems the most practical course. In particular, because large scale refactoring of the code base is underway, it is impractical to remember all the details of several implementations that were used in past years (many of which precede the era in which code review required adequate documentation, modularity, and test coverage), current implementations, and the proposed future implementations. Bugs and developer conflicts have been introduced because of such lapses in understanding, documentation, and test coverage.

Future: It may become feasible to support release branches for longer periods. We have identified several improvements that will make this feasible; the transition to a modular C++14 library needs to be substantially complete, the test infrastructure must be

contained in the source-code repository, an automated suite of performance tests must be available and automated, and a wide range of simulation quality tests must be available and automated. When a GROMACS library API is developed (which is a key outcome of a funded NIH project), then we will consider whether the point of long term support becomes the version (or level) of the API, rather than the release version, and again the existence of automated testing and the stability of the GROMACS source-code infrastructure will be key components in this decision.

4. HADDOCK development process

[HADDOCK](#) is an integrative, information-driven docking approach that supports a large variety of data from biochemical, biophysical and bioinformatics methods (e.g. mutagenesis data, NMR chemical shift perturbations, cross-links from MS, EPR-derived distances, cryo-EM densities, and bioinformatics co-evolution predictions). The software is made available through a user-friendly web interface (<http://haddock.science.uu.nl>), which has attracted a large user community worldwide (13500+ users) and resulted in over 120 deposited structures of complexes in the PDB [8]. HADDOCK has demonstrated a strong performance in the blind docking experiment CAPRI (<http://www.capri-docking.org>), belonging to the best performing approaches and is currently the most cited software in the protein-protein docking field [9]. The HADDOCK software is available both for download and as a web-server. The stable release of the software and web server is HADDOCK 2.2 (<http://www.bonvinlab.org/software/haddock2.2/>), but with a public mature beta version 2.4 (<https://nestor.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4/> - temporary URL) which will become the official production version during 2019.

Internally, HADDOCK is separated in two components, whose interdependence is depicted in Figure 2. A high-level Python layer manages job submission and pre- and post-processing steps. The webservice implementation adds several pre- and post-processing steps to this Python layer that are currently not available in the standalone version of the software. The performance-critical molecular mechanics computations and structural and energetics analyses are performed using the CNS (Crystallography & NMR System) engine (<http://cns-online.org/>), which includes its own scripting language. This high-level language means that in most of the cases, development does not require coding in the original language of CNS (FORTRAN77). Some FORTRAN77 routines specific to HADDOCK are provided with the standalone software and require re-compiling the CNS executable.

Figure 2 Workflow description of (A) the HADDOCK web portal, and (B) the internal workflow of HADDOCK itself.

Most of the developments in HADDOCK over the years have been triggered by scientific questions posed by users and by the core team when working on collaborative projects. Smaller developments occur more often at the level of the force field and associated topologies, namely adding support for new molecules and amino-acids post-translational modifications. These updates are usually triggered by user requests and in the current development process, these will not typically trigger a new software or web server release because of the complexity and importance of maintaining a stable version of the current web server for its users. We are also operating a development server

where the latest changes / additions are implemented and tested. Any new addition to the supported molecules and modifications thereof is added to the server page providing the list of supported modified amino acids.

The actual computations are performed using the CNS engine. All the docking and refinement protocols in HADDOCK are coded at the level of CNS scripts. This means development, as previously stated, does not require coding in the CNS source code (Fortran77) unless new functions need to be implemented at the core level. CNS itself comes with its own suite of tests that should be run after recompilation. We trust that if those tests are successfully passed, CNS will provide reliable results. However, this does not ensure full reproducibility since compilation with different compilers and/or execution on different hardware will inevitably result in small numerical differences due to the stochastic nature of the computations performed. To ensure patched CNS functionality, we perform regression tests of the full HADDOCK protocol to assess the quality of the results.

The development process in HADDOCK is illustrated in Figure 3. Most of the developments are taking place at the CNS scripting level (e.g. the recent implementation of a cryo-EM restrained docking protocol). The parsing of data, models, and the actual computations, including the various docking stages and the final analysis are mainly coded in a collection of CNS scripts amounting to about 80,000 lines of code. A [description of the various stages](#) of the docking protocol, with reference to the CNS scripts called, is provided in the [online manual](#) (currently only for v2.2). Any change in those scripts require running a suite of tests to ensure that the code is not broken, nor are special scenarios affected (see *testing requirements* below). Changes at the Python level are typically less frequent and mostly required when support for new types of experimental data is added, or the number of molecules supported is extended. To ensure best practices in software development, changes are tracked using various public and private GitHub repositories, available through the HADDOCK GitHub organization (<https://github.com/haddock/>).

Figure 3 HADDOCK development workflow

4.1 Copyright and License

Current: HADDOCK v2.X is currently released under a [proprietary license](#) which allows its use for academic research without fee. Commercial applications, usage for non-academic purposes, and/or by for profit entities require the agreement of a commercial license. The required CNS software must be purchased separately directly from the commercial vendor if needed. Note that in both cases the source code is provided to users for local installation, modifications and inspection.

Future: The new, HADDOCK3.X modular version which is being developed in the context of BioExcel2 has been released under Apache 2 License (<https://github.com/haddock/haddock3>). This implies that under BioExcel2 will we will investigate switching from a commercial license of HADDOCK for industry to freely available software, with a possible paid support/consulting mechanism.

4.2 Release process

New features are implemented in local development versions of the software and then pushed to the production version on the server(s) where the web frontend(s) is(are) operating, when tested properly. The translation of local development to production (web portal) is the limiting factor in the HADDOCK release cycle, since the framework used to build the portal in versions prior to 2.4 was not scalable, custom-made, and poorly documented. To avoid those limitations, the web portal has been rewritten in version 2.4 to 1) make use of the Flask framework and 2) automatically update the web forms from the standalone software. Together, these changes allow a faster implementation of new features in the web portal.

All components of the HADDOCK software are version-controlled using Git and GitHub. Each major release is stored under its own branch. Development of new features usually requires forking and creating new feature (spike) branches (e.g. cryo-EM support), while small bug fixes and improvements are directly committed to the main branch after testing and review through pull-requests. Each developer works on a fork of the main repository and issues pull requests when their changes are ready to be merged. Rights to commit changes and pull requesting is granted to a small number of core developers. Acceptance of a pull request requires the approval of at least one other core developer, although minor bug fixes and changes are often accepted and committed without this revision process if automated tests are successful passed. We require all changes to be properly documented, in terms of commit messages and code comments, and self-contained and atomic, to ease making release notes and reverting changes in case of problems. The web server code is now also under continuous integration using Jenkins (see section 4.8.4 below).

Within BioExcel-2, for the release of the HADDOCK code, we have adopted the GROMACS example of versioning, with year and month of release. Releases are however not quarterly as for GROMACS, but only when the code has changed sufficiently to justify it (latest release is *HADDOCK v2.4-2020.09*). We have also added to the web portal in the *server information section* the information about which release of the code is currently running (see <https://bianca.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4>). Similarly, the json file generated by the server containing all parameter and input data now also contain this information (`"haddock_version": "v2.4-2020.09"`).

4.2.1 Deprecation

Within BioExcel1 HADDOCK implemented a deprecation policy. All references and entry points to the various web portals are updated to point to the latest official release and a note is added to the older versions clearly stating the end date of the service and support (at least 6 months before the planned retirement). This led to the retirement of the old 2.1 version of the HADDOCK portals.

4.2.2 Retirement of old versions

While the development branch of HADDOCK is constantly updated as new features are added, the officially distributed standalone version is kept in sync with the one in production for the web portals, since this allows for a much smoother user support by pointing users to try the web portal in case of local installation problems or setup issues.

We use a *major.minor* version numbering system, where changes in the major version do not imply backwards compatibility. The current stable server version is 2.2, with [2.4 public beta](#) being online, but undergoing final fine tuning before publishing as the official production version, planned later 2019. Once this new version will be officially in production, we will support the old 2.2 portals for one year. Users and third-party developers making use of the HADDOCK portal will then be given twelve and six-month notices before the removal of the 2.2 version from our web portals.

Within BioExcell and following the same policy in this new iteration of BioExcel, we implemented a retirement policy that supports and maintains a previous version of the software and of the associated web portal for two and one years, respectively, after the release of a new version of those. While one year might seem rather long for the web portal, our web portals are not updated that often (except for minor fixes), and this is also needed since the duration of research projects might be quite long and it is important to allow users to complete their research work using one and the same version of the software for consistency.

4.3 Software Architecture

The HADDOCK web server architecture is quite static: The server machinery drives the local work, starting the HADDOCK Python process which drives the CNS-based computations, by submission to a local batch system or to distributed grid/cloud resources. For the local version, in order to move to exascale and allow for efficient, large scale computations (i.e. running thousands of parallel docking runs on various systems), we will have to decouple the pre- and post-processing steps from the core of the computations and also to consider inverting the control to a model in which the entire HADDOCK process is submitted to a batch system, rather than the HADDOCK Python process sending thousands of individual jobs to the batch system.

4.4 Modularization

The HADDOCK workflow is deeply interconnected via a series of scripts which in turn call many CNS protocols. This organization, even as optimized as it is, makes it non-trivial to implement new features and devise custom workflows. Henceforth the future version, HADDOCK3.0 will be completely modular. This modularization will be accomplished by refactoring/rewriting high level scripts to remove unnecessary code dependencies and by creating a rich Python API on top of the CNS machinery to allow high-level workflows. This new composition will allow user-designed runs, combining key aspects of the workflow and even allowing use of custom-made modules. The current workflow is undergoing a thorough documentation for the identification of which parts of the code should be modularized. This is a major change in the software architecture, and will allow the code to get a new, fully open source repository under GitHub and the *HADDOCK Commons* will be established to encourage contributions from third parties.

4.5 Webportal design

The web portal UI/UX has been redesigned towards user-friendliness, providing foldable menus to hide forms when not used. Furthermore, several access levels to the

portal are offered, that only expose a limited or more extended sets of input options depending on the complexity of the scenario. Usability and scenario-specific web forms is something that will remain central in any future development. The new Flask framework being used allows for a much more flexible incorporation of new features into the server. It also implements a continuous validation of user input to catch and report possible problems before submission. The main version of the web portal will remain the new 2.4 version during the duration of BioExcel2. With the development of the new modular code, however, will be implemented when suited new portals built on it, with as first scenario identified a scoring portal to identify near native models out of a pool of docking models.

4.6 Handling of new user feature requests

Current and future: New features are often added as result of new challenges and scientific questions. In most cases users directly contact the developers via email (either directly via our university emails, or through our user support email haddock.support@gmail.com). The <http://ask.bioexcel.eu> HADDOCK forum provides another feedback/requirement mechanism. New feature requests are prioritized based on the scientific interest and expected impact on the user community. Under BioExcel, we started making use of the issue tracking mechanism offered by GitHub to add and track internal feature requests. GitHub allows to classify issues in various categories, including *enhancement*, which is best used for feature requests. This allow referring to individual issues when committing code changes to the HADDOCK GitHub repository that address a feature request.

4.7 Handling of bug tracking

Current and future: Under BioExcel we started making us of the GitHub issue tracker to add and track bugs. This allows referring to them when committing software in the HADDOCK GitHub repository that fixes the bug and increasing transparency of the process. This bug tracking mechanism is only internal to the core developers at the moment (for web front-end), but will be public for modular HADDOCK (<https://github.com/haddock/haddock3>) once the repository becomes public.

4.8 Development process details

Any new development should be linked to an identified feature documented as an issue in GitHub. This allows for discussion, planning and review as the work on a feature progress for core developers at BonvinLab and former developers lab members who are still interested in contributing. The following steps are typically followed:

1. Identify and describe a new feature/development by creating an issue classified as *“enhancement”* in the *haddock* GitHub repository.
2. Write a development/implementation plan and solicit feedback from the HADDOCK developers (eventually, if needed from other BioExcel experts).
3. Plan tests, implementing either regression tests in case of changes at the CNS script level in HADDOCK (i.e. new tests/examples running the complete HADDOCK workflow), or unit tests if new functionalities are

added to CNS (i.e. self-contained CNS test scripts testing the specific new feature implemented).

4. Attempt implementation and testing by creating a new branch of the latest stable release of HADDOCK.
5. Finish code, add test and example to the test/example suite.
6. Run the full test/example suite for validation.
7. Submit to main developer for review.
8. Merge code upon approval.
9. Run the entire test/example suite in the merged version for final validation.

Any developments affecting the web portal will follow the same mechanism, with the additional requirement that single, self-contained *haddockparameter json* files will be generated to test automatically the new feature via the “file submit” interface of the web portal. The new 2.4 portal is already under continuous integration using Jenkins which means that changes to the code trigger a *validation pipeline* (see below section 4.8.4). Depending on the impact of a new feature and the number of new features implemented, either a minor update of the software/portal or a major release will be rolled out. We will follow a six-month release policy, with two major releases per year (2.4-year-month), but with intermediary releases if required.

4.8.1 Version control

Git is used for version control. For the initial stage of the development the merge-based GitHub workflow is employed. A stable master branch will be used to create builds. All changes are done on a separate branch. Feature branches are merged into master branch through merge requests. Before the review process an automatic build and testing procedure is triggered via Jenkins/nosetools (already in place for the new server code, will be implemented for the new modular code). A three-level testing procedure is used. The first level of testing is the **unit testing** checking the validity of code changes introduced in separate modules. After the successful passing of unit tests, a set of **integration tests** is triggered. Finally, the **test coverage** analysis is performed using *gcov*. The testing procedure is handled by the Gitlab continuous integration system. An approval of at least two members of the development team is needed to fulfill the merge request.

4.8.2 Testing requirements

Any bug fixes should be validated by running the **test suite** in the local version, assuring all tests are in green.

Any new feature should be accompanied with a well-documented test and example with all required input data and an example output file.

Any feature/bug fix pushed to the web portal should be first tested and validated on the development version of the web portal, demonstrating that the full workflow is running properly, and similar results are obtained. For new features, a single, self-contained HADDOCK parameter (json format) file should be provided by the same developer to allow simple testing via the “file upload” interface of the server.

4.8.3 Testing process of the core HADDOCK code

HADDOCK development currently uses a private repository on GitHub. Test modules are separated from the code in their own GitHub repository. These run the full workflow for the local version of the software with reduced settings to make sure that everything is working properly, allowing to execute the complete test suite in less than one hour on a laptop. Examples for various scenarios are separated from the code in their own GitHub repository. These run the full workflow with standard or optimal setting for the various scenarios to make sure that all the molecule types supported, and the various combination of input data are properly working. Next to testing the entire HADDOCK workflow, unit tests are defined for the CNS software used as the computational engine interpreting and executing the HADDOCK scripts. CNS come with its own test suite that checks that the compiled executable properly works, testing all various commands, modules, and energy functions. Any update pushed to the web portal, should first be successfully tested on the development version of the web portal, ensuring that the various scenarios provided in the example set are all successfully running on the web portal, including the pre- and post-processing steps not offered by the standalone version of the software. Those files are added to the test suite on GitHub. Note that this is a computationally demanding process since full runs should be performed at this stage, which will typically take days to over one week to complete depending on the number of example cases and the load on our server.

4.8.4 Continuous integration of the new webserver code.

A Continuous Delivery (CD) pipeline has been setup to ensure that any change in the code (under the form of a commit or a Pull Request) will trigger a *build*, *test* and *validation* of the whole web server. The whole CD pipeline is illustrated below.

Figure 4 HADDOCK2.4 Continuous Delivery pipeline

This pipeline involves links between GitHub, our repository hosting service, and Jenkins (<https://jenkins.io/>), a self-hosted automation server. This is all automated and event-driven, triggering feedback to the developers via a dedicated Slack channel and emails.

Jenkins is using Pipelines (<https://jenkins.io/doc/book/pipeline/>) to setup an environment as close as possible from the production environment. This is made possible thanks to the web server containerization via Docker. Deploying the Docker containers that bundle the web server within Jenkins allows creating an environment similar to the one used in production. Then a test suite is run and finally a status code is sent to GitHub to report the success or failure of the current code.

4.8.5 Approach to integrate new code

The HADDOCK developers will work on their own separate branch of the code using standard GitHub mechanisms for this. Once all tests and validation have been successfully performed on the local branch, a pull request is done in GitHub to merge the changes in the main branch. GitHub automatically checks if an automated merge can be performed, which needs to be approved by the main reviewer(s). If this is not the case, manual merging will be required, which will involve the developer putting in the merge request and the main/core reviewer(s). This effectively means merging the current official branch and the developer's branch into a new branch that will require another round of tests to make sure the integration was successful. Only then will it be merged into the master branch.

4.8.6 Code documentation, commenting and style

Code is commented with a view to explaining what the code is doing and why a specific part was added, rather than how. If it is not obvious how the code is working, then the naming of variables and methods should be improved. HADDOCK is consisting mainly of Python code and CNS scripts, with some additional C code and a collection of various scripts (*csh*, *sh*, *awk*, *perl*). For the Python part we aim at following the Google Python style guide (<http://google.github.io/styleguide/pyguide.html>). For the CNS scripts, proper indenting, commenting and clear variable naming should be followed.

5. PMX development process

pmx is a Python based software package [10,11] that provides utilities for handling biomolecular structure and topology files directly compatible with GROMACS. The particular strength of the pmx libraries lies in their application to the hybrid structure and topology generation for alchemical single topology based free energy simulations. The automated pmx procedures readily allow the calculation of free energy changes due to amino acid mutations in several contemporary molecular mechanics force fields [12]. DNA nucleic acid mutations are also available via the pmx infrastructure [13]. The basic scheme underlying the workflow of the automated hybrid structure/topology generation is depicted in Figure 5. Preparation of the system for alchemical molecular dynamics simulations following this scheme is available via a command line interface. A user-friendly web-based infrastructure implementing the outlined workflow is available [14]. pmx also enables hybrid structure/topology generation for arbitrary molecules, which makes it particularly attractive for application aiming at drug design and lead optimization.

Figure 5 Workflow of the pmx based hybrid structure/topology generation for an amino acid.

5.1 Copyright and licence

pmx is licensed under the GPU Lesser General Public License v3.0.

5.2 Software architecture

pmx implements a number of classes for the structure and topology handling (Figure 6). The setup for the alchemical single topology simulations of the amino acid, DNA or ligand modifications comprises a number of scripts (Figure 5) that utilize the data structures in Figure 6. All the utilities provided by pmx are available via a command-line interface. The amino acid and DNA nucleic acid mutation setup is also available as an online web-server: <http://pmx.mpibpc.mpg.de/>. Online access to the other features is planned for future development.

Figure 6 The main classes underlying the pmx architecture.

5.3 Release process

During the period of BioExcel-1, the releases were primarily guided by the implementation of new features and bug-fixes. There are two major releases planned over the course of BioExcel-2. In 2019, the final Python 2 based pmx release will be made. This release will be further supported only by providing bug-fixes, but no new features for this pmx version will be developed. In 2020, a Python 3 based pmx release is planned. This version will be supported in terms of bug-fixes and new features. The updates will be pushed onto GitHub at <https://github.com/deGrootLab/pmx>. The master branch will contain the Python 3 based pmx version where the bug-fixes will be pushed as soon as implemented and tested. Active development of the new features will continue on the “development” branch. The version control and documentation of the changes is provided by the Git version control system.

5.3.1 Deprecation

Feature and force-field support deprecation in pmx takes place upon major release. Currently, deprecation is accepted only after a newer version of the same feature/force-field is implemented in pmx.

5.3.2 Retirement of old versions

Old pmx versions are retired upon new major pmx release. The final Python 2 based pmx version is planned to be released in 2019. With the next Python 3 based

pmx release (planned for 2020), the Python 2 pmx will be retired. The addition of new features is stimulated by the scientific questions that are to be solved. Also, updates are considered upon request from the user side. The requests can be sent by email directly to the developers or posted on GitHub. The testing process (described below) serves as the main method for identifying bugs.

5.4 Development process details

5.4.1 Review process

pmx employs at most two developers at a time, thus no independent review process is implemented.

5.4.2 Testing requirements

The first level check for a newly generated mutation library: the hybrid topology needs to contain all the bond/angle/dihedral parameters of the non-hybrid topologies representing physical states.

Second level check: test cases have been set up that must yield zero as computed free energy. The majority of errors that can occur will lead to deviations from zero and therefore these calculations provide an excellent quality control: these thermodynamic cycles must converge to zero for every new mutation library and software version.

Similarly, closing thermodynamic cycles for ligand topologies is the main criterion to be met for the hybrid structure/topology generation for arbitrary small molecules.

Furthermore, starting with the pmx release based on Python 3, unit testing will be added to cover the major classes, modules and functions of pmx.

5.4.3 Testing process

Currently the testing is performed internally after generating new mutation libraries, feature updates and incorporating new rules for the arbitrary molecule hybrid structure/topology generation. Over the period of BioExcel-1, the tests have been partially automated. Further test automation will be continued over the course of BioExcel-2. The created testing infrastructure will be shipped together with pmx making it possible for the users to validate their own generated mutation libraries and ligand topologies.

5.4.4 Approach to integrate new features

The bug-fixes and new features are integrated into the master branch as soon as they pass the testing phase.

5.4.5 Code documentation and commenting

The current pmx source code contains a bare minimum of comments. With every major pmx release the commenting of the code will be improved following Python's docstring convention. This will allow for the automated documentation of the major modules, classes and functions in pmx.

5.4.6 Coding standards and coding style

The current pmx version is written in Python 2. The major release planned for 2020 will introduce pmx based on Python 3. The current pmx code does not adhere to any

specific style recommendations, but tries to maintain an understandable class, method and variable naming convention. This has proven a robust and extendable framework since the first release in 2010.

6. CP2K QM/MM development process

CP2K is a popular, state-of-the-art free and open source European package for Density Functional Theory and related methods, with a wide range of capabilities and excellent performance. It can be used to address problems in materials science, computational chemistry and, more recently, biomolecular research. It provides a framework for multiple modelling methods including hybrid (QM/MM) calculations useful for biological systems.

Before discussing our approach to development on CP2K in the project, it is helpful to note a few things about how the CP2K fits in the BioExcel project.

CP2K has been identified as a code that is likely to be increasingly important for the Biomolecular research community. Unlike GROMACS and HADDOCK however, the lead developers of CP2K are not part of the BioExcel project. This introduces the potential for certain challenges around ensuring that our contributions are aligned with those of the lead developers, and also the depth of knowledge around previous work undertaken on the code. On the other hand, as the CoE grows, there will be a need to work on an increasing number of codes, and a model which allows us to work with developers outside the project is probably more flexible and scalable than requiring that lead developers of all the codes we develop be employed by, or directly funded by the CoE. There is obviously a clear benefit to having GROMACS and HADDOCK's developers integrated so closely with BioExcel, but this can be complemented with an approach that allows us to directly engage with the wider biomolecular software community through development on other codes.

Another difference between CP2K and the codes listed above is that we have brought the code into the Centre during the second phase of funding for the CoE. Whereas we have been working with GROMACS and HADDOCK in the CoE for the past three years (and for years before this as independent partners), BioExcel have been working on the code since January 2019. Partners in the project *have* been actively involved in the development and use of CP2K in the past, but the point from which we are starting in this project is different. This also explains why we have undertaken a performance and scalability analysis of the code early in the project to ensure that our plans for the project are appropriate and impactful.

CP2K is an open source project with multiple contributors. Key developers are listed at <https://github.com/orgs/cp2k/people>. During the project we will work with this team to try to ensure that our contributions are introduced into the main CP2K codebase, and not provided simply as a fork to the codebase that is harder to sustain and support. Our planned approach is to work with the existing development processes of the code, making suggestions for improvements where appropriate to align with the best practice being promoted in BioExcel. In the remainder of Section 4, we therefore outline the approaches and policies of CP2K as they currently stand.

Our work on CP2K will be focused on areas that are relevant to the Biomolecular research community, and we will look at areas – such as the QM/MM interface – that are of particular interest to our community. In terms of performance and scalability improvements, it is possible that bottlenecks identified will result from a core part of the code. Large-scale changes of the main structure of the CP2K code are out-of-scope for BioExcel, but if changes of this nature would appear to be necessary to allow improved scalability and performance of *biomolecular-relevant components* of the code we will make recommendations to the lead developers and, where appropriate, look for other funding opportunities with these developers to address the issue.

6.1 Copyright and License

CP2K code uses a GPL version 3 license (see <https://www.cp2k.org/about> and <https://www.cp2k.org/download> for details). BioExcel’s contributions to the code would be made available under the same license.

6.2 Versioning policy

The trunk of CP2K is updated regularly (sometimes multiple times a day) on GitHub. A stable release version is generated roughly once per year. For benchmarking and profiling carried out by EPCC the latest stable release (6.1), released 11 June 2018 was used.

It is likely that other users of the code may have older versions, as it will largely depend on what is installed/available on the HPC systems to which they have access.

Any modifications to the code will need to be made by forking the master branch of the source code (at <https://github.com/cp2k/cp2k>) and then following the process described in section 5.6.1.

6.3 Handling of new user feature requests

Feature requests are handled via the GitHub issue tracker at: <https://github.com/cp2k/cp2k/issues>. If necessary, additional BioExcel2 specific feature requests will be tracked via the BioExcel2 project GitHub, which could also be used for development issues that relate to any new code, tests or components that have not yet been incorporated into the main CP2K codebase.

6.4 Handling of bug tracking

Bug tracking for the code is handled via the GitHub issue tracker at: <https://github.com/cp2k/cp2k/issues>. BioExcel will not be responsible for fixing bugs in the wider codebase. Bugs will be considered for fixing if (i) they are reported by a BioExcel user in the context of BioExcel work (for example, on a use case), or (ii) they result from or relate to code developed in BioExcel. The process for monitoring and fixing bugs will change over the course of the project. Earlier in the project, the bug tracker will be monitored to look for bugs in parts of the code that are being studied in the context of performance and scalability improvements (primarily those related to the QM/MM interface) to ensure that any changes made remain meaningful once the bug

is fixed. Simple bug fixes could be incorporated into code changes that relate to performance. Later in the project, the bug tracker will be monitored in order to fix any bugs arising from BioExcel's contribution to the code,

6.5 Code architecture and design

CP2K is written in Fortran 2003 and can be run using a combination of MPI and multi-threading (OpenMP) and also with CUDA. However, not all of the code contains OpenMP directives or CUDA instructions and thus it depends on the particular type of problem being run as to whether a pure MPI approach or a combination of MPI + “something else” is appropriate.

CP2K can thus be built in different ways, depending on the parallelism instruction sets desired. Below is the terminology commonly used to describe CP2K **builds**:

SOPT = serial build

POPT = pure MPI parallel build

SSMP = pure OpenMP build

SDBG = serial debug build

PSMP = parallel MPI + OpenMP build

The work described in this report relates to QM/MM type simulations and focuses on the MPI + OpenMP build of the code. This is often referred to in the literature as the PSMP build, standing for parallel SMP as it uses both MPI and OpenMP.

In general, the PSMP build is the most flexible as it can be run with a single thread as an MPI code but also with multiple threads if appropriate. As such we plan to work with the PSMP build and to conform to the existing architecture and design wherever possible.

6.6 Development process details

6.6.1 Review process

The main process for submitting changes to the source code is by submitting a Pull Request from a fork on GitHub to the CP2K master branch – from there members of the code development team can then approve/accept/reject the changes.

There is a Continuous Integration system in place to check conventions and running automated checks on the Pull Requests.

The developers use ``git rebase`` to keep the Git history linear, meaning that in your final Pull Request there cannot be any merge commits, please see <https://github.com/cp2k/cp2k/wiki/Git-Tips-&-Tricks> for details on this.

Any code changes should adhere to the coding conventions listed at: <https://www.cp2k.org/dev:codingconventions>. To apply the coding conventions on code changes, developers can run the commands ``make pretty`` & ``make doxify`` on the source code.

6.6.2 Testing requirements

CP2K has over 3000 regression tests located in the source code *tests/* directory, which must be run prior to submitting any changes to main trunk. Only when all the tests have passed can your code be accepted.

A dashboard detailing the results of the regression tests on a number of different systems and compiler versions is located at <https://dashboard.cp2k.org/>.

This dashboard can serve as a good source of information when building CP2K for the first time as it provides information regarding which compilers the code is stable with and also if particular commits have any issues when working with the master release.

6.6.3 Code documentation, commenting, standards, and style

Details of the coding standards expected for CP2K can be found at: <https://www.cp2k.org/dev:codingconventions>. BioExcel will conform to these conventions for our contributions.

6.7 Benchmarking and profiling

As mentioned above, as a starting point to understand the baseline performance of the code on which we will build, an initial benchmarking and profiling exercise has been undertaken with biomolecular-motivated test cases to identify in more detail relevant areas of the code on which to concentrate performance and scalability improvements.

This work was undertaken primarily as an internal exercise to better assess the viability of increasing the scalability of CP2K for these biomolecular use cases, and not as a benchmarking study presented for the use of the wider community. For this reason, the report describes all of the work undertaken and does not focus only on the final results.

This section includes the benchmarking and profiling performed on the CP2K application code. We begin by describing the test cases that will be used to benchmark, present results from the benchmarking and finally present the results of profiling the code using a subset of the test cases.

6.7.1 Benchmarking

This section includes the initial benchmarking of CP2K for QM/MM type systems.

We have built CP2K version 6.1 and all its associated libraries (libint, libxc, libgrid, libxsmm, ELPA, FFTW (Cirrus only)) on ARCHER and Cirrus. On both machines we have built a PSMP build of CP2K, that is one that includes both MPI and OpenMP so we can investigate both pure MPI and MPI + OpenMP performance.

The results presented in this report have been obtained using both the SISU system and the ARCHER systems. ARCHER 2 [15][16] comprises 4920 Cray XC30 compute nodes with Intel Xeon E5-2697 v2 (12 core, dual-socket chips running at 2.7 GHz) with 64 GB of RAM on 4544 nodes and 128 GB of RAM on the remaining 376 nodes. SISU [17] is composed of 1688 Xc40 Scalar compute nodes and each node has 12-core Intel (Xeon) Haswell (E5-2690v3, 64bits) with 64GB-DDR4 memory on each node.

Sample CP2K ARCH files for building CP2K on these systems can be found at: https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_use_cases/tree/master/cp2k_arch_files

Eight test cases were constructed to reflect BioExcel use cases, which investigate the QM/MM problem. These have been uploaded to the project GitHub repository, https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_use_cases. The test case input files can be found in two tarfiles, *Scale-QM.tgz* and *Scale-MM.tgz* at: https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_use_cases/tree/master/CP2K-inputfiles

Sample shell scripts for running the test cases can be found under: https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_use_cases/tree/master/CP2K-inputfiles/batchscripts

The tests cases compute a short QM/MM production run of 5 MD steps in the NVT ensemble for an equilibrated system. The classical electrostatics are controlled using Smoothed Particle Mesh Ewald (SPME) summation. The QM part of the system is described using the Gaussian and Plane Waves (GPW) method with planewave cutoff of 300Ry, basis set DZVP and BLYP functional to compute the exchange-correlation energy. The QM/MM coupling is described electrostatically using the S-WAVE scheme and GEEP library to generate the Gaussian expansion of the MM potential. The GEEP library is one component of the code that was considered a good candidate for development. We thus included this in all the QM test cases.

The test cases comprise two components, one that investigates the QM problem and one that investigates the MM problem. With the QM tests the total number of atoms is held constant and the number of atoms included in the QM problem is increased. With MM tests the number of atoms is increased with everything else (except the box size) is kept constant.

The convention for naming the tests is to use *Test* followed by the type of problem being investigated (*QM* or *MM*) along with the number of atoms in either the QM or MM part respectively. Thus *Test-QM-20* corresponds to a QM test with 20 atoms in the QM part and *Test-MM-30928* corresponds to an MM problem with 30928 atoms in the MM part of the computation.

Table 1 and Table 2 summarize the QM and MM test cases respectively and also include the original timings obtained on the SISU system. For the QM scaling tests, the number of QM atoms is picked to be typical of what actual researchers would use, although it

² Note: when building and testing the code on ARCHER we discovered that the `fftw/3.3.4.11` module resulted in a performance degradation of up to 20% with the H2O-64 test case. Using module `cray-fftw/3.3.6.3` resolved this issue.

is possible that up to 100 QM atoms may be tested in the future. For the MM scaling tests the number of atoms depends on the size of the protein being studied, but in general we estimate most problems would consist of a system containing 100,000 atoms.

Table 1 Details of QM test cases. The runtimes were as initially obtained using the SISU machine at JYU.

Test name	Total number of atoms	Number of QM atoms	CP2K runtime on 192 MPI procs (s)
Test-QM-20	28264	20	401
Test-QM-32	28264	32	489
Test-QM-53	28264	53	470
Test-QM-77	28264	77	517

Table 2 Details of MM test cases. The runtimes were obtained using the SISU machine at JYU. Test-MM-30928 and Test-MM-51034 were run with LSD enabled. Test-MM-112498 and Test-MM-297610 were run with LSD disabled.

Test name	Total number of atoms	CP2K runtime on 192 MPI procs (s)
Test-MM-30928	30928	525
Test-MM-51034	51034	538
Test-MM-112498	112498	413
Test-MM-297610	297610	556

Initial observations of results on the SISU machine showed some unexpected results, particularly for the MM tests where one would naively expect that as the number of atoms increase the runtime should also increase. Further investigation revealed that some tests had been run with the LSD flag set and others without.

Following discussion with between partners it was decided that all the tests should be run without LSD enabled as there is no clear science case for including the LSD computation.

For comparison Table 3 and Table 4 show the runtimes obtained on the ARCHER system for the QM and MM tests with and without LSD on 192 MPI processes.

Table 3 Comparison of QM performance with and without LSD enabled on ARCHER. For all tests the number of atoms is fixed at 28264. All tests were run on 192 MPI processes of ARCHER and repeated three times with the best time of three runs taken.

Test name	Number of QM atoms	CP2K runtime (s) no LSD	CP2K runtime (s) with LSD
Test-QM-20	20	445	581
Test-QM-32	32	465	614
Test-QM-53	53	523	717
Test-QM-77	77	573	748

Table 4 Comparison of MM performance with and without LSD enabled on ARCHER. All tests were run on 192 MPI processes of ARCHER and repeated three times with the best time of three runs taken.

Test name	Number of atoms	CP2K runtime (s) no LSD	CP2K runtime (s) with LSD
Test-MM-30928	30928	472	601
Test-MM-51034	51034	449	587
Test-MM-112498	112498	479	649
Test-MM-297610	297610	639	766

Looking at the results in Table 3 and Table 4 we can see that the general trend is that the runtime increases with the number of QM atoms used and with the number of atoms in the MM tests. However, the scaling is not linear, i.e. doubling the number of QM or MM atoms does not result in a factor of two increase in runtime. Furthermore, the MM runtimes do not increase monotonically with system size (c.f. the runtimes from *Test-MM-30928* and *Test-MM-51034*). This anomaly was investigated and repeated tests illustrated the same behavior. Because of this we have opted to focus our scaling tests on the smallest and largest tests for both QM and MM as they provide the largest difference in runtime and therefore any differences in *where* the code is spending its time are likely to be easier to capture from these tests.

We have investigated the scaling of the QM problem using *Test-QM-20* and *Test-QM-77*. We have measured the performance of CP2K from 2 up to 64 nodes of ARCHER, testing all feasible permutations of MPI processes and OpenMP threads. Figure 7 shows the performance for *Test-QM-20*.

Figure 7 Performance of Test-QM-20 on ARCHER for 5 time steps. All thread and process combinations are tested to investigate whether using multiple threads is beneficial.

From Figure 7 we can see that once we exceed four nodes, the best performance is always obtained using 6 OpenMP threads. This is an important result as if a scientist opts to run a *pure MPI* version of CP2K they could be losing out significantly, as the *threaded* version of the code can give much better performance. The scaling of *Test-QM-20* is relatively poor suggesting that even at small numbers of nodes we are already hitting some significant performance bottlenecks.

Figure 8 shows the corresponding performance plot for *Test-QM-77*. As with *Test-QM-20* we see a crossover point where threads become beneficial over the pure MPI runs. As *Test-QM-77* has a larger number of QM atoms (77 in *Test-QM-77* compared with 20 in *Test-QM-20*) the crossover now occurs at a large number of nodes, as now we need more nodes in order to fit the problem into memory and thus benefit from the OpenMP threading. As with *Test-QM-20* the scaling of *Test-QM-77* is up to around 16 nodes on ARCHER. These results are consistent with previous benchmarking on problems of a similar size and nature such as the Faylite-FIST benchmark³.

³ <https://www.cp2k.org/performance>

Figure 8 Performance of Test-QM-77 for ARCHER for 5 time steps. The crossover point between where the threaded version helps occurs around 8 nodes.

The corresponding performance for *Test-MM-30928* and *Test-MM-297910* are given by Figure 9 and Figure 10 respectively.

Figure 9 Test-MM-30928 performance on ARCHER for 5 time steps. The crossover point occurs around 4-6 nodes.

Figure 10 Test-MM-297910 performance on ARCHER for 5 time steps. The crossover point occurs around 16 nodes. Note that there is no result for the pure MPI run on 2 nodes as this failed with an out of memory (OOM) error.

Again, the behaviour is very similar to that observed with the QM tests. In each case the threaded performance exceeds that of the pure MPI performance once the number of nodes used is such that the problem can fit into memory and thus take advantage of the OpenMP in the code. As with the QM test cases, the scaling for the two MM test cases is relatively poor.

Although the scaling of CP2K is poor for both the QM and MM test cases the addition of OpenMP threads can give us a significant reduction in runtime, especially as we approach the limit of MPI scaling. For example, consider *Test-QM-20* on 10 nodes, the fastest pure MPI runtime was 424 seconds with the six threaded run taking 367 seconds. This is a reduction in runtime of 13%.

As an aid to scientists using the code for running QM or MM type problems Figure 11 shows the “best” option for running the QM and MM problems.

Figure 11 Best performance guide for the QM (top plot) and MM (bottom plot) test cases plotted against the number of nodes used. The figures are intended to be a guide to researchers wanting to know whether a pure MPI run or combination of MPI + OpenMP will perform best. The text plotted next to each data point indicates whether a

pure MPI or threaded run (denoted NTH, where N is 2, 4 or 6 threads per MPI process) performed best for a given number of nodes.

All the BioExcel test cases run for just 5 time steps. Typically, a real QM or MM simulation would run for many more steps (e.g. 1000 to 5000). To obtain an estimate of what the total runtime for a large run we can use the output from the *.ener file that CP2K creates for each run, which includes the elapsed time for each step.

Table 5 shows the Elapsed Time per step as obtained from the .ener file for *Test-QM-20* on 24 MPI processes.

*Table 5 Example of timings in the *.ener file allowing the startup costs to be estimated. Time step 1 includes the start up cost and the cost of that step. Time steps 2 through 5 average out at 110.9 seconds and thus discounting this from time step 1 gives us a start up cost of roughly 258 seconds.*

Step	Elapsed Time (s)
0	0.0
1	369
2	111
3	111
4	110
5	111

Looking at the timings in Table 5 we can see that for steps 2 through 5 the time taken per step is consistent and averages out at 111 seconds. The time taken for step 1 however includes both the startup cost *and* the time for that time step and thus we can estimate the startup costs to be approximately 369-111 i.e. 258 seconds. The total CP2K runtime for this configuration was 824 seconds meaning that the start up costs account for nearly 30% of our total runtime. Whilst in a real simulation this would be unimportant it is a significant consideration when benchmarking or profiling the code using these tests cases.

Using the timings contained in the .ener file we have computed an estimate of the startup costs for each of the QM and MM test cases examined in this report. In each case we've used the .ener file that corresponded to our "best" run for a given number of nodes and then computed the startup costs as detailed above. Figure 12 shows the percentage of runtime spent in startup for each of the test cases considered.

Figure 12 Startup costs for the QM and MM test cases given as a percentage of the CP2K time (seconds). For each number of nodes the "best" result was used.

For reference we include Figure 13, which shows the performance of *Test-QM-20* with (solid lines, filled symbols) and without (dashed lines, open symbols) the startup costs.

Figure 13 Performance of Test-QM-20 comparing the total CP2K time (solid lines, filled symbols) with the same data with the startup costs removed (dashed lines, open symbols).

The startup cost is relatively stable with increasing number of nodes and the scaling limit has already been reached at the larger node counts. This means that removing the startup costs from the performance plot actually just has the effect of shifting the values down the y-axis and thus the shape of the performance plots, scaling behaviour etc for the different test cases does not significantly change and thus our interpretations made including the startup costs remain valid.

However, for carrying out profiling experiments it may be harder to deal with the startup costs as they are likely to skew our profiles and could lead us to concentrate on areas of the code that would not be an issue for real science users of the code.

A possible solution would be to run our tests for sufficient time steps that the startup costs become insignificant e.g. such that they account for around 5% of the total runtime. It may also be possible to profile the code in such a way that the profiling is only activated from time step 2 which we will incorporate in further studies.

6.7.2 Profiling

We have used the Cray profiling tool suite (CrayPat) to obtain profiles of CP2K for *Test-QM-20* and *Test-MM-30928*.

In order to prevent the startup costs from dominating the profiles we have used our startup costs obtained from a 5 step run to compute the number of time steps required to reduce the startup time to around 5% of the total runtime. For all the tests considered it turns out that 40 time steps is sufficient to keep the startup costs below 5% and thus our profiles have all been obtained using 40 time steps.

We have obtained profiles on two nodes (a pure MPI run using 48 MPI processes) where the MPI scaling is still relatively good and also on eight nodes where the MPI scaling is tailing off. On eight nodes we have obtained profiles for both the pure MPI case (192 MPI processes) and also for the best performing configuration on eight nodes, which was obtained when, using 32 MPI processes each running 6 OpenMP threads.

When profiling CP2K we wanted to investigate if particular routines are causing performance bottlenecks in the computation and also to try, if possible, to understand the issues with the MPI scaling.

We have investigated the breakdown of time spent in User Code (heading “USER”), the time spent in the Programming Model (e.g. MPI and/or OpenMP) (heading “MPI”) and the time spent in any additional libraries that are either not part of the CP2K source code or that CrayPat couldn’t instrument (heading “ETC”). CrayPat also gives an estimate of the overhead caused by the profiler itself (heading “RT”).

For our run on two nodes with 48 MPI processes Figure 14 shows the overview profile for *Test-QM-20* as presented by Cray’s Apprentice2 application.

Figure 14 Overview plot of profile obtained with *Test-QM-20* running for 40 time steps on 2 nodes of ARCHER. 48 MPI processes and 1 OpenMP thread used.

From Figure 14 we can see that on two nodes most of the time CP2K runtime (85.33%) is spent doing useful computation with only 13.58% spent doing communications.

If we now look at Figure 15 showing the breakdown of time spent in different parts of the code as given by CrayPat we can see that two routines (highlighted) are taking over 5% of the total runtime and thus may warrant further investigation.

Samp%	Samp	Imb. Samp	Imb. Samp%	Group Function PE=HIDE
100.0%	464,710.0	--	--	Total

68.7%	319,151.2	--	--	USER

12.6%	58,760.8	3,611.2	5.9%	pw_spline_utils_MOD_pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc._omp_fn.0
8.3%	38,451.2	2,199.8	5.5%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_integral_ab
4.9%	22,588.9	572.1	2.5%	__fast_MOD_zero_c2._omp_fn.1
4.1%	19,278.7	283.3	1.5%	__fft_tools_MOD_x_to_yz._omp_fn.14
2.9%	13,352.5	724.5	5.3%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_gather_p._omp_fn.22
2.8%	13,116.8	627.2	4.7%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_zero
2.7%	12,701.4	640.6	4.9%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_scatter_p._omp_fn.24
2.6%	12,302.4	759.6	5.9%	__kahan_sum_MOD_kahan_sum_d3
2.3%	10,552.4	375.6	3.5%	__fft_tools_MOD_yz_to_x._omp_fn.9
2.1%	9,988.7	14.3	0.1%	
qmmm_gp_w_energy_MOD_qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_lr				
2.0%	9,485.7	568.3	5.8%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_axpy
1.9%	8,659.3	608.7	6.7%	__fast_MOD_zero_c3._omp_fn.0
1.8%	8,400.4	25.6	0.3%	
qmmm_gp_w_forces_MOD_qmmm_force_with_gaussian_low				
1.4%	6,620.2	101.8	1.5%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_coarse2fine
1.4%	6,557.5	87.5	1.3%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_fine2coarse
1.4%	6,537.9	166.1	2.5%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_copy._omp_fn.46
1.0%	4,874.6	184.4	3.7%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_derive._omp_fn.38
1.0%	4,851.5	141.5	2.9%	__fast_MOD_copy_rc._omp_fn.2

16.6%	77,101.3	--	--	ETC

6.9%	31,979.7	24,876.3	44.7%	apply
5.1%	23,713.3	40,695.7	64.5%	_int_malloc

13.6%	63,080.3	--	--	MPI

8.1%	37,516.9	1,959.1	5.1%	mpi_alltoallv
3.4%	15,879.9	2,316.1	13.0%	MPI_ALLREDUCE
1.4%	6,367.6	1,259.4	16.9%	MPI_WAITANY

1.1%	5,065.1	--	--	RT

1.1%	5,059.2	158.8	3.1%	munmap

Figure 15 Profiler output for Test-QM-20 running for 40 time steps on 2 nodes of ARCHER using 48 MPI processes and 1 OpenMP thread.

In Figure 15 and all subsequent CrayPat profiles, the first two columns, labelled “Samp%” and “Samp” give the percentage of the total runtime and number of samples (computed from the mean of samples computed across all parallel tasks). Columns three and four labelled “Imb. Samp” and “Imb. Samp%” give amount of imbalance of the routine across all parallel tasks as computed from the minimum and maximum number of samples. Column five gives the routine name.

The profile for the *Test-MM-30928* is given in Figure 16. The same two routines are found to be the most costly.

Samp%	Samp	Imb. Samp	Imb. Samp%	Group Function PE=HIDE
100.0%	462,173.4	--	--	Total

69.3%	320,231.9	--	--	USER

12.7%	58,737.8	3,024.2	5.0%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc._omp_fn.0
8.3%	38,226.6	1,902.4	4.8%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_integral_ab
4.9%	22,473.9	584.1	2.6%	__fast_MOD_zero_c2._omp_fn.1
4.2%	19,192.8	159.2	0.8%	__fft_tools_MOD_x_to_yz._omp_fn.14
2.8%	13,159.2	552.8	4.1%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_gather_p._omp_fn.22
2.8%	12,987.7	504.3	3.8%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_zero
2.7%	12,564.7	411.3	3.2%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_scatter_p._omp_fn.24
2.6%	12,060.9	786.1	6.2%	__kahan_sum_MOD_kahan_sum_d3
2.4%	10,930.7	6.3	0.1%	

2.3%	10,486.1	360.9	3.4%	__fft_tools_MOD_yz_to_x._omp_fn.9
2.0%	9,315.9	514.1	5.3%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_axpy
2.0%	9,194.5	22.5	0.2%	

1.9%	8,664.2	527.8	5.9%	__fast_MOD_zero_c3._omp_fn.0
1.4%	6,585.5	109.5	1.7%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_coarse2fine
1.4%	6,552.4	54.6	0.8%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_fine2coarse
1.4%	6,492.1	147.9	2.3%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_copy._omp_fn.46
1.0%	4,838.4	112.6	2.3%	__fast_MOD_copy_rc._omp_fn.2
1.0%	4,824.7	145.3	3.0%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_derive._omp_fn.38

16.8%	77,534.9	--	--	ETC

6.5%	29,845.1	27,524.9	49.0%	apply
6.0%	27,834.6	38,005.4	59.0%	_int_malloc

12.8%	59,043.4	--	--	MPI

8.6%	39,821.3	2,137.7	5.2%	mpi_alltoallv
2.6%	12,051.3	2,458.7	17.3%	MPI_ALLREDUCE
1.1%	5,070.9	864.1	14.9%	MPI_WAITANY

1.1%	5,044.8	--	--	RT

1.1%	5,039.0	182.0	3.6%	munmap

Figure 16 Profiler output for Test-MM-30928 running for 40 time steps on 2 nodes of ARCHER using 48 MPI processes and 1 OpenMP thread.

These two test cases are constructed to follow similar run paths, and have been observed to have the same routines critical for performance. So we will therefore restrict further consideration of the small test cases to the QM profiles.

From Figure 15 the two most costly routines on two nodes were found to be `__pw_spline_utils_MOD_pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc._omp_fn.0` and `__pw_methods_MOD_pw_integral_ab` taking 12.6% and 8.3% of the total runtime respectively. The CrayPat profiler gives the full name of the routine, which includes the module name in which the routine is contained and the name of the routine (function or subroutine) itself. The most costly routines are located as follows:

`pw_integral_ab` is a function located inside the `src/pw` directory in the module file `pw_methods.F`.

`pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc` is a subroutine located in the `src/pw` directory in the module file `pw_spline_utils.F`. This subroutine contains a large OpenMP parallel region which when the code is run on multiple threads can result in a significant speedup.

Future work will involve investigating whether any performance improvements can be obtained inside these two routines.

We now look at the performance on eight nodes and compare it against the two node results to see if we can get any understanding as to why the scaling is so poor. Table 6 summarizes the time spent in different parts of CP2K on two and eight nodes. On eight nodes we've included results from two different configurations, a pure MPI run on 192 processes and a mixed mode MPI + OpenMP run on 32 MPI processes each running 6 threads. This was the best performing configuration on eight nodes.

Table 6 Breakdown of time spent in different components of CP2K for Test-QM-20 on different number of nodes.

Configuration profiled	Wallclock time (s)	USER (%)	MPI (%)	ETC (%)	RT(%)	USER + ETC (%)
2 nodes: 48 MPI procs, 1 OpenMP thread	4702.61	68.7	13.6	16.6	1.1	85.3
8 nodes: 192 MPI procs, 1 OpenMP threads	2896.76	68.9	22.1	7.0	1.8	75.9
8 nodes: 32 MPI procs, 6 OpenMP threads	2490.24	52.0	33.3	12.3	2.2	64.3

From Table 6 we can see that for a pure MPI run, as we increase the number of nodes, the time spent in communications increases from 13.6% to 22%. When we run with a combination of MPI + OpenMP the total runtime decreases by 14% relative to the pure MPI time, but the time spent in communications rises to 33.3%.

This can be explained as follows. The threaded run has fewer MPI processes (32 instead of 192) and thus the number and size of messages that need to be transferred changes. The total number of messages is reduced (~179.3 million on 192 processes compared with ~6.8 million on 32 processes running 6 threads) but the size of the messages are larger (192 processes have an average message size of 186 bytes versus 1492 bytes for the 32 processes running thread configuration) and thus more time is spent sending these large messages between processes (“MPI” column). However, the increase in time spent doing communications is considerably less than the benefit obtained from being able to utilise OpenMP in a number of the computationally intensive routines. In particular the number of samples the profiler spends in routine `pw_nn_compose_no_pbc` is nearly six times less for the multi-threaded run than the number of samples reported by the pure MPI run.

For completeness we have included the text profile output for the eight node runs on 192 MPI processes (Figure 17) and also on 32 MPI processes running 6 OpenMP threads (Figure 18).

Samp%	Samp	Imb. Samp	Imb. Samp%	Group	Function
					PE=HIDE
100.0%	278,896.0	--	--	Total	

68.9%	192,249.5	--	--	USER	

21.3%	59,474.5	4,992.5	7.8%		

pw_spline_utils_MOD_pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc._omp_fn.0					
13.3%	37,157.0	2,561.0	6.5%		__pw_methods_MOD_pw_integral_ab
4.6%	12,874.7	871.3	6.4%		__pw_methods_MOD_pw_zero
4.4%	12,146.2	924.8	7.1%		__kahan_sum_MOD_kahan_sum_d3
3.3%	9,273.6	606.4	6.2%		__pw_methods_MOD_pw_axpy
2.4%	6,667.6	132.4	2.0%		__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_coarse2fine
2.4%	6,570.3	76.7	1.2%		__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_fine2coarse
2.0%	5,456.8	232.2	4.1%		__fast_MOD_zero_c2._omp_fn.1
1.4%	3,934.0	409.0	9.5%		__pw_spline_utils_MOD_find_coeffs
1.2%	3,415.5	1,121.5	24.8%		__fft_tools_MOD_x_to_yz._omp_fn.14
1.2%	3,411.6	119.4	3.4%		__pw_methods_MOD_pw_scatter_p._omp_fn.24
1.1%	3,123.4	128.6	4.0%		__pw_methods_MOD_pw_gather_p._omp_fn.22
=====					
22.1%	61,534.5	--	--	MPI	

11.8%	32,862.4	1,304.6	3.8%		mpi_alltoallv
6.8%	18,985.0	3,029.0	13.8%		MPI_ALLREDUCE
1.4%	3,885.3	779.7	16.8%		MPI_WAITANY
=====					
7.0%	19,555.8	--	--	ETC	

2.2%	6,104.3	12,518.7	67.6%		__int_malloc
2.1%	5,889.5	8,571.5	59.6%		apply
=====					
1.8%	5,023.8	--	--	RT	

1.8%	5,018.0	158.0	3.1%		munmap
=====					

Figure 17 Profiler output for Test-QM-20 running for 40 time steps on 8 nodes of ARCHER using 192 MPI processes and 1 OpenMP thread.

If we look at the time spent in MPI calls obtained from the various different profiles we find that collective operations such as `MPI_Alltoall` and `MPI_Allreduce` dominate. This is perhaps not surprisingly as these are typically the operations involved in carrying out Fast Fourier Transforms (FFT) and FFT's are known to be required for many of the computations carried out by codes such as CP2K.

Samp%	Samp	Imb. Samp	Imb. Samp%	Group	Function
100.0%	246,535.3	--	--	Total	PE=HIDE Thread=HIDE

52.0%	128,247.4	--	--	USER	

10.2%	25,048.3	1,042.7	4.1%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_integral_ab	
5.5%	13,538.4	43.6	0.3%	__qmmm_gpww_energy_MOD_qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_lr	
4.6%	11,376.6	58.4	0.5%	__qmmm_gpww_forces_MOD_qmmm_force_with_gaussian_low	
3.5%	8,724.5	207.5	2.4%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc_omp_fn.0	
2.9%	7,155.4	641.6	8.5%	__kahan_sum_MOD_kahan_sum_d3	
2.3%	5,708.2	27.8	0.5%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_fine2coarse	
2.2%	5,342.6	31.4	0.6%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_coarse2fine	
2.1%	5,119.0	342.0	6.5%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_zero	
2.0%	5,051.0	900.0	15.6%	__fast_MOD_zero_c2_omp_fn.1	
1.9%	4,580.9	483.1	9.8%	__fft_tools_MOD_x_to_yz_omp_fn.14	
1.8%	4,510.9	558.1	11.4%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_axpy	
1.2%	3,055.2	102.8	3.4%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_gather_p_omp_fn.22	
1.1%	2,751.4	579.6	18.0%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_scatter_p_omp_fn.24	
1.0%	2,499.2	186.8	7.2%	__fft_tools_MOD_yz_to_x_omp_fn.9	
=====					
33.3%	82,173.7	--	--	MPI	

15.1%	37,189.2	2,168.8	5.7%	MPI_ALLREDUCE	
11.8%	29,168.6	990.4	3.4%	mpi_alltoallv	
3.2%	7,967.5	815.5	9.6%	MPI_WAITANY	
1.6%	3,910.4	451.6	10.7%	mpi_waitall	
=====					
12.3%	30,245.2	--	--	ETC	

4.9%	12,047.1	812.9	6.5%	apply	
2.1%	5,179.9	1,213.1	19.6%	gomp_team_barrier_wait_end	
1.2%	2,909.1	115.9	4.0%	gotoblas_daxpy_k_sandybridge	
=====					
2.2%	5,473.9	--	--	RT	

2.2%	5,428.4	729.6	12.2%	munmap	
=====					

Figure 18 Profiler output for Test-QM-20 running for 40 time steps on 8 nodes of ARCHER using 32 MPI processes and 6 OpenMP threads.

One possible area to investigate to improve the MPI scaling is whether any optimizations can be made to these collective operations. The CrayPat profiler provides some advice regarding the optimal MPI process placement configurations for point-to-point communications however it does not tell us anything as to whether altering the process placement can help for the collectives. Following discussions with the Cray Centre of Excellence team at EPCC it has been suggested that some experimentation with process placement may help along with experimenting with some of the MPICH settings relating to collectives. We are currently waiting for the Cray team to provide us with more information on this.

Our final investigations look at how the profiles of CP2K vary as we increase the number of QM or MM atoms. To do this we run both the smallest and largest tests for QM and MM problems on a fixed number of nodes and compare the profiles for a pure MPI run. For the QM tests we can perform this comparison using two nodes. However, for the MM tests we need to use four nodes as the pure MPI configuration couldn't fit into memory on two nodes. The results for QM and MM are summarized in Table 7 and Table 8 respectively.

Table 7 Summary of the time spent in different components of CP2K for Test-QM-20 and Test-QM-77 on two nodes. Test-QM-20 has 20 QM atoms, Test-QM-77 has 77 QM atoms. For Test-QM-77 there is no time reported for the profiler overhead, RT, as it was smaller than 1% of the total runtime.

Configuration profiled	Wallclock time (s)	USER (%)	MPI (%)	ETC (%)	RT(%)	USER + ETC (%)
2 nodes: 48 MPI procs, 1 OpenMP thread. Test-QM-20	4703	68.7	13.6	16.6	1.1	85.3
2 nodes: 48 MPI procs, 1 OpenMP thread. Test-QM-77	6694	63.5	16.0	19.3	-	82.8

From Table 7 increasing the number of QM atoms by a factor of almost four results in slightly less time being spent in useful computation and slightly more time in communications. The most expensive routines are still found to be `pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc` and `pw_integral_ab`, which for *Test-QM-77* account for 8.9% and 6.0% of the runtime respectively.

Table 8 Summary of the time spent in different components of CP2K for Test-MM-30928 and Test-MM-297910 on two nodes. Test-MM-30928 has 30928 atoms and Test-MM-297910 has 297610 atoms.

Configuration profiled	Wallclock time (s)	USER (%)	MPI (%)	ETC (%)	RT(%)	USER + ETC (%)
4 nodes: 48 MPI procs, 1 OpenMP thread. Test-MM-30928	3365	69.0	18.3	10.5	1.5	79.5
4 nodes: 48 MPI procs, 1 OpenMP thread. Test-MM-297610	4283	75.1	13.8	9.0	1.2	84.1

Examining Table 8 we can see that increasing the number of MM atoms by a factor of nearly 10 also has little impact on the breakdown of time spent doing computation and communication. As four nodes is already getting close to where scaling degrades the smaller *Test-MM-30928* spends proportionately more time in communications (“MPI”) compared to *Test-MM-297910*.

Figure 19 shows the profile for *Test-MM-30928* run on four nodes of ARCHER using 96 MPI processes. Looking at the time spent in user code we see that the most costly routines are still found to be `pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc` and `pw_integral_ab`. As the total number of atoms is very similar to that used for the QM tests this is what we expect.

Samp%	Samp	Imb. Samp	Imb. Samp%	Group Function PE=HIDE
100.0%	331,008.6	--	--	Total

69.0%	228,455.3	--	--	USER

17.7%	58,434.2	4,166.8	6.7%	
pw_spline_utils_MOD_pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc_omp_fn.0				
11.2%	36,980.1	2,232.9	5.8%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_integral_ab
3.9%	12,745.5	665.5	5.0%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_zero
3.6%	12,025.4	809.6	6.4%	__kahan_sum_MOD_kahan_sum_d3
3.2%	10,611.0	265.0	2.5%	__fast_MOD_zero_c2_omp_fn.1
2.7%	9,092.7	520.3	5.5%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_axpy
2.1%	6,940.1	821.9	10.7%	__fft_tools_MOD_x_to_yz_omp_fn.14
2.0%	6,595.1	111.9	1.7%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_coarse2fine
2.0%	6,538.9	61.1	0.9%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_fine2coarse
2.0%	6,521.8	203.2	3.1%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_scatter_p_omp_fn.24
1.9%	6,358.2	263.8	4.0%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_gather_p_omp_fn.22
1.7%	5,465.9	6.1	0.1%	
qmmm_gpww_energy_MOD_qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_lr				
1.4%	4,604.6	45.4	1.0%	
qmmm_gpww_forces_MOD_qmmm_force_with_gaussian_low				
1.2%	4,105.6	393.4	8.8%	__fft_tools_MOD_yz_to_x_omp_fn.9
1.2%	3,816.6	400.4	9.6%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_find_coeffs
1.1%	3,805.2	433.8	10.3%	__fast_MOD_zero_c3_omp_fn.0
=====				
18.3%	60,635.7	--	--	MPI

9.7%	31,951.3	1,673.7	5.0%	mpi_alltoallv
5.5%	18,120.3	3,816.7	17.6%	MPI_ALLREDUCE
1.5%	5,026.8	1,007.2	16.9%	MPI_WAITANY
1.2%	3,861.2	776.8	16.9%	mpi_waitall

10.5%	34,830.1	--	--	ETC

3.5%	11,480.0	11,571.0	50.7%	apply
3.4%	11,264.3	18,732.7	63.1%	__int_malloc

1.5%	4,998.9	--	--	RT

1.5%	4,992.8	181.2	3.5%	munmap

Figure 19 Profiler output for Test-MM-30928 running for 40 time steps on 4 nodes of ARCHER using 96 MPI processes and 1 OpenMP thread per process.

Further Figure 20 shows the profile for Test-MM-297910. This test uses nearly ten times the number of atoms in the classical part of the computation compared with any of the other profiles examined so far and thus we expect to see some difference in the routines executed.

		Samp	Samp%	Function
PE=HIDE				
100.0%	422,923.4	--	--	Total

75.1%	317,809.4	--	--	USER

13.8%	58,213.4	4,238.6	6.9%	

				__pw_spline_utils_MOD_pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc._omp_fn.0
12.4%	52,623.2	16.8	0.0%	__qmmm_gpww_energy_MOD_qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_lr
10.5%	44,265.4	89.6	0.2%	

				qmmm_gpww_forces_MOD_qmmm_force_with_gaussian_low
8.8%	37,353.4	4,385.6	10.6%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_integral_ab
3.0%	12,751.9	1,608.1	11.3%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_zero
2.9%	12,099.6	1,258.4	9.5%	__kahan_sum_MOD_kahan_sum_d3
2.3%	9,910.3	318.7	3.1%	__fast_MOD_zero_c2._omp_fn.1
2.2%	9,172.3	1,117.7	11.0%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_axpy
1.6%	6,603.6	114.4	1.7%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_coarse2fine
1.6%	6,586.1	756.9	10.4%	__fft_tools_MOD_x_to_yz._omp_fn.14
1.5%	6,538.3	49.7	0.8%	__pw_spline_utils_MOD_add_fine2coarse
1.5%	6,191.3	374.7	5.8%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_gather_p._omp_fn.22
1.5%	6,157.1	248.9	3.9%	__pw_methods_MOD_pw_scatter_p._omp_fn.24
=====				
13.8%	58,397.6	--	--	MPI

6.8%	28,867.6	1,547.4	5.1%	mpi_alltoallv
5.0%	21,166.3	3,357.7	13.8%	MPI_ALLREDUCE
1.1%	4,772.3	1,252.7	21.0%	MPI_WAITANY
=====				
9.0%	38,086.6	--	--	ETC

3.1%	13,076.0	8,941.0	41.0%	apply
2.1%	8,710.0	20,721.0	71.1%	_int_malloc
=====				
1.2%	4,963.4	--	--	RT

1.2%	4,957.6	209.4	4.1%	munmap
=====				

Figure 20 Profiler output for Test-MM-297910 running for 40 time steps on 4 nodes of ARCHER using 96 MPI processes and 1 OpenMP thread.

In *Test-MM-297910* the routines using more than 5% of the runtime are: `pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc`, `qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_lr`, `qmmm_force_with_gaussian_low` and `pw_integral_ab`. On 4 nodes these routines account for 45% of the total runtime. Thus in addition to `pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc` and `pw_integral_ab` we are now spending a significant amount of time in two routines involved in the more classical part of the computation, i.e. the two routines starting `qmmm_*`. Therefore, these two routines should also be investigated for possible optimizations.

One important additional observation is that the profiles obtained above do not provide any specific evidence to support the idea that GEEP would be a particularly good candidate for performance improvements. Whilst it may still be true that there is scope for improvement with this library, the results above suggest that GEEP is not a limiting factor for this type of calculation. In the next steps below we note that a further comparison should be undertaken with calculations with GEEP turned off so that the specific impact of GEEP can be ascertained.

6.7.3 Summary and Next Steps

We have benchmarked and profiled CP2K using a number of test cases designed to investigate the QM and MM scaling of a QM/MM type model. We have identified four routines that would benefit from further investigation and possible optimization and/or

parallelization. We have also observed that the MPI scaling is relatively poor for the test cases investigated and made some suggestions as to how this might be improved.

An observation based on the results above is that there is not just a single part of the code that is an obvious candidate routine for improvement that would have a significant impact on the code's performance, despite the limited scaling performance observed. The most obvious bottleneck observed accounts for only roughly 5% of the runtime, and CP2K has a relatively flat profile. This may reflect the fact that many key routines have already been worked on and optimized in the past.

That said, `pw_nn_compose_r_no_pbc` and `pw_integral_ab` do take significantly more than 5% of the total runtime when running Test-QM-20 or Test-MM-30928 on 192 MPI processes with one OpenMP thread. Furthermore when we looked at the largest of the MM tests, Test-MM-297910 we observed that the routines `qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_lr` and `qmmm_force_with_gaussian_low` also took well over 10% of the total runtime and that thus it should be these four routines that are investigated further.

Although there are ways forward here, the results obtained here highlight a risk that obtaining meaningful scalability improvements in the scope of the project may be challenging. In order to mitigate this risk, we have decided that a decision will be made at PM8 to determine whether greater impact could be made by concentrating development efforts elsewhere, for instance in those tasks in the WP which address portability, usability, and readiness for future systems. If this course of action is taken, the reasons for this decision will be written up and made available so that others can repeat the analysis undertaken and learn from the work undertaken in the project.

In the meantime, the next steps will be as follows:

- Gather more profiling data for a wider range of numbers of nodes (focusing initially on pure MPI runs), looking at time spent in *user*, *etc* and *mpi* to observe where individual routines stop scaling, and to explore the region beyond where the code scales to confirm which routines are most problematic
- Further analyse the four costly routines identified above to determine possible improvements
- Run tests with GPU acceleration, and determine whether GPU acceleration could benefit the routines identified above
- Run tests with GEEP turned *off* to obtain a baseline confirm whether there is a qualitative difference to scaling when the GEEP libraries are used
- Discuss ideas in more detail with other CP2K developers and look at the code history for the routines identified above to determine whether any previous attempts have been made to optimize these routines
- Run tests to evaluate I/O performance, and in particular to ensure that the test cases that have been used for the initial benchmarks adequately capture any potential issues such as those that have previously been identified with the Faylite-FIST benchmark⁴

⁴ See, e.g., <https://www.cp2k.org/performance>

- Compare test case results with existing CP2K benchmarks⁴ to determine whether the test case is sufficiently different to include as a new CP2K benchmark, and if so, to propose to the CP2K team that a new benchmark be included

7. Scientific software lifecycle management

Software lifecycle management involves the specification and execution of processes related to code requirements, implementation, delivery, maintenance, depreciation etc. Many models have been developed over the years (see e.g. https://www.tutorialspoint.com/sdlc/sdlc_overview.htm). Some models such as the waterfall, iterative and agile methods have been more widely applied than others. The specific choice of a model depends very strongly on the type of developer and user community. E.g. Open-source community codes have much different needs and requirements than closed-source commercial ones sold as products. Target audiences, developer team sizes etc. are some of the major factors influencing the choice of model.

It is challenging to apply some of the common models to academic software development processes (see e.g. <https://drops.dagstuhl.de/opus/volltexte/2017/7146/>). There is much less separation between users and developers than in general software engineering. Most of the time all developers of an academic scientific research software are also users of that software. They are developing it for other users who have a similar background (e.g. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7656273.1> and <http://oro.open.ac.uk/17673/>). Feature development depends on scientific method development and its outcomes. Delivery timelines also do not reflect common commercial practices (such as “we need to release it before the launch of the new gaming console” etc.). Developer teams are often a handful of researchers for whom code development is part of broader range of research activities. These, and other factors, make many of the common models inapplicable and even counter-productive in academic environment.

Still, considerable interactions between researchers and computer software engineers over the years have led to major uptake of software development best practices by the academic communities, even the emergence of a “research software engineer” position in many academic institutions. A lot of effort has been put into promoting the best practices and professionalization of academic software, most notably the work of the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI, www.software.ac.uk).

BioExcel is a strong proponent of the application of those best practices. We published a white paper on the topic (<https://zenodo.org/record/1194634>) where we have presented the development models for each of the core applications. In the paper we have covered all aspects of the development process such as feature request handling, design, implementation, version control, review process, integration approach, release processes, depreciation, retirement etc. The processes present real scenarios of code development in an academic setting. In future work, we are planning to release an update of the white paper and produce an educational webinar on the topic. We believe that our experience will be of great value to developer teams who are not so familiar with those practices.

8. Quality Assurance of Software

Adoption of best practices for software development is important but we need also a framework to assess the quality of the code and the processes related to its management. In collaboration with SSI, BioExcel has begun work on such framework and a quality mark which allows code developers to self-assess their products using a list of criteria. The scores from the assessment will be presented in an easy to grasp visual form, which will allow developers to monitor their progress, as well as to compare with other projects. In addition, we will develop a quality mark for software as a service (SaaS) where we derive criteria based on established software management frameworks such as FitSM. The quality marks will be described in the upcoming deliverable “D5.1 - Branding and Quality Mark Design Inception Report”. In future work, both quality marks will be incorporated into an online tool for self-assessment.

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Appendix: Status of core codes

Annex 1: HADDOCK code (production) development status

- Complete
 - Work in progress

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
Official distribution version	v2.2	v2.4 (4 releases, latest is September)	
Development version(s)	v2.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> v2.5 (port to python3) v3.0 (complete modular rewrite) 	
Supported features in v2.4			
• Cryo-EM restraints	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
• Support for up to 20 molecules	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Distance-dependent dielectric	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• C6 symmetry restraints	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Coarse graining for proteins	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Coarse graining for nucleic acids	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Support for cyclic peptides	no	planned	
• Support for glycosylated proteins	no		
• Support for glycan docking	no		
• Automatic detection of D-amino acids	no	planned	
• Option for automatically definition of HIS protonation states based on electrostatic energy	no	planned	
• Switched to official 1/2 letter code for RNA/DNA	no	planned	
• Option to fix molecules in their original position	no	planned	

• Support for shape restraints	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Containerization (Singularity)	no	planned	
Increased efficiency in v2.4			
• Various analysis options for increased efficiency	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Removal of bottlenecks in workflow machinery to all more concurrent docking runs (a covid19 response)	no	planned	
• Packing in Singularity and integration with PyCOMMPs	no	planned	
• Improved error detection and handling for more robust execution	no	planned	
Code Health			
• Version control (GitHub)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Integration tests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Semantic versioning	no	planned	
• Code quality - Linter, logging	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> - v2.5	
• Submodule integration (tests/examples)	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Annex 2: HADDOCK web portal development status

- Complete
 - Work in progress

Note: The HADDOCK v2.2 webserver has gone into maintenance mode after the end of Bioexcel 1, meaning no new feature will be implemented.

	End of BioExcel1		HADDOCK2.4 PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
	v2.2	v2.4	v2.4	
Status	Production	Development	Production	
Web Server Features				
• Docker integration	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Continuous Integration pipeline (Jenkins)	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Single Sign On (via EGI CheckIn)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Interactive result pages	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• GDPR compliant	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Heavy validation of input parameters	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Molecule type-specific optimal settings	no	no	planned	
• User workspace	no	no	planned	
• Refinement interface	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	no	planned	
File submission (reproducible parameter file)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	no	planned	
• New molecule type: Shape	no	no	planned	
• New molecule type: Dummy	no	no	planned	
• New molecule type: Glycan	no	no	planned	

• New molecule type: Glycosylated Proteins	no	no	planned	
• Reporting API	no	no		

Annex 3: HADDOCK3.0 new modular code development status

- Complete
 - Work in progress

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
Live status	-	Development	
Development version	-	alpha 2	
Modules			
• Pre-processing	-	Planned	
• Topology generation	-	Planned	
• Rigid Body sampling	-	Planned	
• Semi flexible refinement	-	Planned	
• Solvent explicit refinement	-	Planned	
• Scoring		Planned	
Supported restraints			
• Distance restraints	-	Planned	

Annex 4: GROMACS code development status

- Complete
 - Work in progress

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
Official distribution version	v2019	v2020.4	
Development version(s)	release-2020	release-2021	
Supported features			
• Python API	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (v0.1)	Planned (v0.2)	
• Modular simulator	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Density fitting	no	planned	
• Accelerated weight histogram sampling method	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• AWH free-energy perturbation	no		planned
• Multiple time stepping on CPU	no		planned
• Multiple time stepping on GPU	no		planned
• GPU only simulations	no	planned	
• Update groups	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• OpenCL PME offloading	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• Intel iGPU OpenCL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• ARM SVE Support	no		planned
• SYCL Support	no		planned
• Non-bonded benchmark tool	no	planned	
• Stochastic cell rescaling	no		planned
• Containerization (Docker/Singularity)	no	planned	
• QM/MM interface to CP2K	no	planned	

• Topology pre-processing for QM/MM	no	planned	
• Nudged-Elastic-Band reaction pathway optimizer	no		planned
Code Health			
• Version control (Gerrit/GitLab)	☑	planned	
• Unit tests	☑	planned	
• Integration tests	☑	planned	
• Semantic versioning	☑	planned	
• Code quality - clang format, clang-tidy, doxygen	☑	planned	
• Quarterly KPI checking (removal of legacy code, cyclomatic complexity)	no	planned	
• User feedback integration label	no	planned	
• Submodule integration (tests/examples)	no		planned
• Physical validation suite	☑	planned	
• Integration of QM/MM into build and testing environment	no		planned

Annex 5: GROMACS modular code development status

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
Live status	v2019	v2020	
Development version	release-2020	release-2021	
Modules			
• MDModules	☑	planned	
• fine-grained modularisation	no	no	

• Trajectory analysis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
• mdrun	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> planned	
• Defined API boundary	no		planned

Annex 6: PMX status

- Complete

- Work in progress

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
pmx webservice: main framework	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
pmx webservice: amino acid mutations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
pmx webservice: DNA mutations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
pmx webservice: tripeptide database	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Ligand modifications: atom mapping	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Ligand modifications: topology generation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Ligand modifications: ligand mapping	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Ligand modifications: cycle closure correction	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Python3: core modules	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Python3: amino acid mutations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Python3: nucleic acid mutations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	planned	
Python3: ligand modifications (atom mapping)		planned	
Python3: ligand modifications (topology generation)		planned	
Python3: ligand modifications (ligand mapping)			Planned

Free energy calculation workflows	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Planned
Absolute free energy support			Planned
Python3: pmx webserver amino acid mutations			Planned
Python3: pmx webserver DNA mutations			
Proline mutation support		planned	
Arbitrary covalent mutation support			

Annex 7: CP2K status

- Complete
 - Work in progress

	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
Addition of functionality to enable GROMACS-CP2K interface		
Add cell size change functionality in CP2K through call to libcp2k to enable pressure coupling with GROMACS	planned	
Optimisation of GEEP QM/MM force & energy subroutines		
Addition of OpenMP-threaded parallelism	planned	
Enabling offload to GPU		
Optimisation of subroutines identified by performance analysis of the GROMACS-CP2K interface		
Optimisation of new DBCSR small matrix multiplication acceleration scheme for biomolecular problems		Planned
Optimisation of further CP2K and/or DBCSR subroutines for CPU & GPU platforms based on analysis of interface performance on range of community test cases	planned	
Improvement of Quickstep DFT load balancing for biomolecular QM/MM		
Updating Quickstep task-based load balancing heuristics		Planned
Implementing on-the-fly load measurement		stretch target